

**APPLICATION OF PHYSIOTHERAPEUTIC FACTORS IN OBSTETRICS AND
GYNECOLOGY**

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Abstract: *Physiotherapy is one of the important components of prevention and treatment of gynecological problems. Not only are procedures with physiotherapeutic properties as effective as possible, but they are also minimally dangerous to the female body. Therefore, physiotherapy is usually used not only as an adjunct, but also as a primary means of treating gynecological diseases.*

Key words: *physiotherapeutic factors, obstetrics and gynecology, electronic and magnetic fields, physiotherapy*

Currently, the following physiotherapy methods are used in gynecology: the use of electric and magnetic fields, the use of electric current, ultrasound, radiation therapy (phototherapy) and the use of manual massage. In gynecology, a physiotherapy laser is often used, which allows you to eliminate inflammation, anesthetize, and enhance tissue regeneration.

In gynecology, physiotherapy is used in the following conditions:

for restorative treatment after gynecological operations;

for rehabilitation after abortion and cultetization of the uterine mucosa;

in the process of preparing women for pregnancy who have had a miscarriage or stillbirth in the past;

To prepare the mucus before IVF;

with chronic inflammation of the uterine tumors;

with infertility due to obstruction of the fallopian tubes.

Physiotherapy in obstetrics and gynecology

Physiotherapeutic agents can be used both during pregnancy (if the doctor has prescribed such treatment) and after childbirth. During pregnancy, physiotherapy can be used to treat early toxicosis, a risk of termination of pregnancy due to high uterine tone. Postpartum physiotherapeutic methods reduce the likelihood of inflammation, accelerate suture recovery, and treat breast fractures and mastitis.

Physiotherapy magnets in gynecology

Magneto therapy is a commonly used physiotherapeutic treatment method to treat inflammation in gynecology. In this case, the woman's body is exposed to an artificially created low-frequency magnetic field and can therefore be variable or constant, impulsive (intermittent) or constant, low or high frequency. The low-frequency magnetic field allows acceleration of oxidation and reduction reactions in the cell and improves blood supply. In addition, the magnetic field can reduce pain, have anti-inflammatory effect, reduce tissue swelling, and stimulate regenerative processes.

Physiotherapy in gynecology

Physiotherapy procedures performed after surgery allow to prevent the formation of adhesions in the organs of the female reproductive system. Often physiotherapy is prescribed to relieve the pain from the adhesion process with spikes.

CMT-physiotherapy in gynecology

CMT-physiotherapy, i.e. the use of sinusoidally modulated currents, is commonly used in gynecology. The essence of this method is the use of a weak alternating current that affects the muscles and nerves, relieves pain, activates peripheral blood flow, improves tissue nutrition, and stimulates development.

Physiotherapy in obstetrics and gynecology are new vessels. The CMT method is used in gynecology to eliminate functional disorders and inflammatory processes.

Infertility in gynecology

With instability, physiotherapy can increase blood flow to the pelvic organs, eliminating pain from adhesions in the fallopian tubes, which can be the cause of infertility. Physiotherapy recovery to eliminate the causes of the disease after surgery achieves the best results of recovery. In addition, it relieves pain and prevents the formation of pimples.

Thus, physiotherapy in gynecology should not be abandoned unless there are contraindications.

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